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project

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Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review the present document.

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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1. Introduction

“Project Ô: demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water” has been funded as an Innovation Action under the H2020 call H2020-CIRC-2017TwoStage, Topic: CIRC-02-2016-2017 - Water in the context of the circular economy.

Project Ô aims at demonstrating¹:

- 1) A novel distributed water network that enables the use of alternative sources of water, such as brackish/salt water, collected rainwater, own/external wastewater owing to the following characteristics:
 - i) Ability to treat efficiently contaminants and pollutants in water otherwise unusable or very costly to use reducing pressure on (natural) resources.
 - ii) High specialisation coupled with modularity of design and closed loop control based on innovative sensors.
 - iii) Small scale specialisation and use of solar power and irradiation allowing the development of mobile plants to deal with low volumes of water difficult to reach.
- 2) A Multi-user Collaborative Platform allowing water systems authorities and regulators as well as water users to evaluate the overall effects of introducing and regulating small water management loops.
- 3) Integrated and participative approaches to water planning involving directly the community and the territory fostering social innovation.

Project Ô has in summary the overall objective of providing stakeholders (everybody using or regulating the use of water in an area) with a toolkit that enables them to plan the use of and utilise the resource water whatever its history and provenance, obtaining significant energy savings in terms of avoided treatment of water and waste water and release of pressure (quantity abstracted and pollution released) over green water sources. This overall objective was demonstrated in up to four sites each in different Countries of Europe and in Israel, involving water utilities, industries, aquaculture and agriculture as well as local authorities of different sizes.

To attain its goals, Project Ô encompasses 10 WPs, among them WP9, “Dissemination and exploitation of results” addresses dissemination, standardization and exploitation issues.

The present document addresses specifically the Dissemination, acknowledged as an important component of the research process, in particular for European Union(EU) funded research projects.

According to the definition given by EU² for H2020 projects Dissemination consists in: “to make the results of a project public (by any appropriate means other than protecting or exploiting them, e.g. scientific publications). where “results” are defined as “Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”³.

Indeed, Dissemination has to facilitate research uptake, understanding and exploitation.

The present document traces the Dissemination action carried out in Project Ô and analyses the results, with particular attention to the multiplicity of activities carried out and the actors involved both as proponents and recipients, and with respect to the Dissemination plan included in the Annex 1 – Description Of Action of Project Ô , that was guiding the Dissemination deployment, starting from the release of Dissemination Plan (DP, D9.1 of Project Ô).

The DP was conceived as a “living document” and, as such, was revised and adapted along the project. The various undertaken activities allowed to progressively build this Final Dissemination Report (FDR) as the evolution of the initial DP.

¹ <http://eu-project-o.eu/the-project> Last accessed November 2022

² <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary> last accessed November 2022

³ Ibidem

A first check-point for the Dissemination action was represented by the Updated Dissemination Plan (UDP), focused on the advances in the Dissemination activities during Project Ô implementation, the variation/integration of the Dissemination strategy, accounting also for the impacts of the pandemic emergency of Covid-19 on Project Ô, affecting all involved partners from March 2020.

The UDP beside critically revising the Dissemination strategy, the specific Dissemination activities and the Dissemination material, shed light on new actions to be introduced to strengthen the Dissemination effectiveness within the European context as well as among the partners.

Through the analysis of the Dissemination activities carried out during the project, this document will review the initial Dissemination strategy backwards, in a perspective that goes beyond the end of the project.

Tracking of Dissemination activities was carried out periodically from the WP9 leader, being the implementation supported by all project partners.

Dissemination goals, strategy and activities can be considered as the three main components of Dissemination action, as represented in the Venn diagram (Figure 1), where we can envisage **tools** at the intersection between “goals” and “strategy”, **targets** at the intersection between “goals” and “activities” and **impact** at the intersection between “strategy” and “activity”

Figure 1. Venn diagram for Dissemination action

In the next paragraphs it will be presented a short summary of goals, strategy and activities, as foreseen in the DP, and the corresponding modifications introduced within the UDP.

2. Dissemination goals

The objectives of the DP have been conceived to:

- a) identify in the context of all the activities carried out within the WPs, the results that are worth to be disseminated, considering the state of the art, the target stakeholders and the issues related to the protection of intellectual property,
- b) gain awareness on Project Ô’s achievements from all stakeholders (see below)

- c) enhance synergies with similar or complementary projects and/or research activities
- d) foster possible future collaborations and avoid duplication of efforts in future research activities
- e) give the EU scientific community the opportunity to build future knowledge on Project Ô's research results and, thus, accelerate innovation and growth
- f) ease the implementation of adequate strategies and practices to the adoption of the proposed solutions
- g) foster the proactive engagement of all the actors involved and the empowerment of potential end-users
- h) ensure an effective dialogue, exchange of knowledge and technical know-how between the stakeholders
- i) foster cross-fertilization between academic units and industries also through the involvement in the project of Early Stage Researchers and PhD students from Universities and Research Institutes

The stakeholder categories that have been identified and targeted in the DP are the following ones:

1) **Scientists:** Dissemination aims to spread the knowledge on the integrated and symbiotic use of water, in order to stimulate interdisciplinary researches and to contribute to the creation of young scientists skilled in the integrated and symbiotic use of water in the transition to the Circular Economy.

2) **Potential users** (particularly public and private water managers, start-ups in water tech, waste water producers, service providers, people from textile and food industries, people from aquaculture and agriculture). The aim is to provide them with a toolkit that enables them to plan the use of water whatever its history and provenance, obtaining significant energy savings in terms of avoided treatment of water and wastewater and release of pressure over green water sources.

3) **Policy makers, Regulators, public and private Investors.** The aim is to propose an innovative model for "water planning" supporting the regulators in implementing policy instruments to identify water efficiency strategies and contribute to create a market for Investors.

All the above goals were maintained in the UDP, where it was envisaged the possibility to involve different categories of stakeholders in common events, for instance in a multidisciplinary School on water reuse based on a systemic approach to the topic, as will be described in details later on.

3. Dissemination strategy

In the Project Ô Dissemination strategy three kind of interactions were considered:

- i) within Project Ô consortium,
- ii) within partners' organisations and networks (including other projects funded under the same call, other EU projects where any Project Ô member is participating, departments, offices, ...),
- iii) within broader community (key stakeholders, general audience).

The interactions were considered bi-directional, meaning that feedback of Dissemination activity contributed to the continuous tuning and improvement of further Dissemination activities to maximize the impact of Project Ô.

Properly addressing the interactions could enhance the effectiveness of the DP, by activating synergies, conveying interests, enlarging knowledge sharing.

The main Dissemination paths envisaged in the Dissemination strategy were described in terms of five categories: What (dissemination content), To whom (target stakeholder), How (Dissemination activity), Expected Impact

(tangible and non-tangible outcomes), Indicators (quantitative measurement, when possible, of the dissemination efficiency and/or effectiveness).

Table 3.1 reports a couple of Dissemination paths as an example.

Table 3.1

What	To whom	How	Expected Impact	Indicators
Research results	Scientists	Publication of papers in high impact international journals dealing with water treatment, management, governance and related issues (standardization, LCA, etc....).	Advanced knowledge in the relevant disciplines Higher reputation inside the scientific community at national and international level	nr. of publications, nr. of citation at medium-long term,
Overview on main aspects of water reuse and Project results	Stakeholders (see paragraph 2)	International School on water reuse	Raise awareness about water re-use/recycle Strengthen relationships between Project Ô's consortium and stakeholders	nr. of appointed people, nr. of country of provenance, satisfaction survey

The UDP evidenced a limit of the Dissemination strategy presented in the DP, consisting in a limited overlap/complementarity between WP9 and WP8 (Communication) activities, due to the fact that the WP8 activity was stopped waiting for the approval of an amendment concerning the entrance of a new partner in the Project Consortium, committed to WP8 deployment. This delay in the amendment approval had a negative impact also on the website management and on the update of documents in both open and restricted area.

Nevertheless, updated information about progresses in Dissemination activities were collected through email exchanges and shared Google documents, allowing to keep updated the picture of the Dissemination activities performed during the Project.

In UDP it was also evidenced the need to stimulate the interaction among Consortium partners, also weakened during the pandemic time by the impossibility to have meeting in presence, usually fostering interactions and suitable for results exploitation also in term of sharing ideas and building-up projects for other calls. Under this point of view, building and foster the widest participation from Consortium members to the International School on Water Reuse represented a relevant asset.

Moreover, the pandemic time not only forced but also improved the capability to fruitfully interact online with project stakeholders as will be discussed later on, when analysing the undertaken activities.

4. Dissemination Activities Planned

Dissemination activities were divided in two main groups:

- i) internal (within the Consortium)
- ii) external

i) In order to foster a fruitful interaction within Consortium partners, several activities were planned:

- Preparation and constant updating of a contact list for the WP9 including at least one person for each partner organization; this allowed to keep all the participants aware of initiatives related to Dissemination.
- Periodical update (every 6 months, tentatively) of the file tracking the Dissemination activities undertaken.

- Periodical WP9 conference (mainly in remote) to foster interaction among the Consortium partners, in order to envisage possible additional outcomes to be disseminated also beyond the specific task of each partner.

ii) According to the Dissemination strategies, several activities aimed to attract stakeholders' attention were planned, as described below.

a) Journal Publications.

Formal reports and scientific articles in open access, peer-reviewed journals.

b) Participation in Conferences and Workshops

This activity represents a suitable opportunity to disseminate project results, in a context suitable to fruitfully discuss them seeking for knowledge sharing, synergies with other ongoing projects, also in view of future collaboration beyond the project duration.

c) Workshop Organizations (Workshop Days in Universities/Industries of partners' organizations or others):

This activity was considered potentially fruitful to enhance visibility of Project intermediate and final results and progresses, to attract interests of scientists and to create awareness in the scientific and industrial community.

d) Industrial conferences.

During project implementation it was considered useful that Project Coordination team plan in order to cover all the main events without duplications and with a clear message consistent with the dissemination and the communication strategy.

e) European official websites, magazines, events.

The use of the official channels offered by EC services was planned to maximize dissemination and to promote Project Ô's project activities.

The publication of a newsletter every six months and its distribution via the Internet, containing information related to both the participants in the project and other researchers in the field, was planned too.

f) Summer school.

The implementation of Summer School was planned, mostly targeting PhD students to extend their skills towards the complex and multidisciplinary topic of water treatment, water reuse and fit for purpose approach.

g) White papers

The possible publication on the webpage of the Project of white papers reporting on data not entering in peer-reviewed papers on scientific journals nor covered by IPR was considered, in order to reach the widest possible audience with the project's results.

h) Website The website release was included in the activities of WP8.

i) Collaboration between ongoing initiatives.

It was planned to contact Projects funded under the same call as well as other projects dealing with water quality, water treatment, water management, in order to implement network activities and collaborative initiatives.

Under this point of view, the involvement of many partners of Project Ô in other projects related to water issues represents an added-value.

In the UDP the former activities have been maintained and a new dissemination external activity has been added, that is the establishment of an International School on Water Reuse, with the First Edition realized by the end of

the Project and next editions in the following years, being therefore the legacy of Project Ô. More details about this School will be given later on in this document.

5. Analysis of Dissemination Activities undertaken during the project

The Dissemination activities have been mapped by periodically collecting information from all partners.

It must be evidenced that the pandemic emergency of Covid-19 significantly affected the project activities, from the onsite implementation of the technologies up to the organization of events and to the participation on events like conferences, seminars, congresses, workshops and schools.

From March 2020 up to the present, events worldwide have been cancelled or postponed. Nevertheless, the pandemic emergency has enhanced online activities and in the R&I field there was a significant resilience to the negative impact of the pandemic emergency that could be evidenced also in the context of Dissemination action. Indeed, an increasing number of online opportunities appeared and thanks to the fast capability to adapt to the new approach, the Dissemination action did not stop, rather modified its way of implementation.

Therefore, several Dissemination events foreseen in the DP for 2020 and 2021 are not present anymore in the updated tables, rather new ones appeared, testifying an overall resilience toward the pandemic period.

a) Journal Publications.

Table 5.1 reports in details the Journal publications. In the DoA of the Project, it was expected the publication of at least 15 papers (some of them might be published within one year after the project end). It can be seen that 18 papers have been already published, while other 7 have been submitted and 1 is in preparation, with a distribution among Consortium partners well in agreement with what it was foreseen in the DoA of the Project.

Table 5.1. List of Journal publications

Partner	Date	Name of the journal	Type of Open Access	Type of material generated	Accomplishment	Title of the material	Link/ Reference/Additional informations	Type of audience reached		
UNITO	2019	Molecules	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Evaluation of the Photocatalytic Activity of a Cordierite Honeycomb Supported TiO2 Film with a Liquid-Solid Photoreactor		Scientific community		
UNITO	2020	ACS CATALYSIS	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Assessing a Photocatalytic Activity Index for TiO2 Colloids by Controlled Periodic Illumination		Scientific community	Industry	
UNITO	2020	Nanomaterials	Green	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Photocatalytic Transformations of 1H-Benzotriazole and Benzotriazole Derivates		Scientific community	Industry	
AAU	2019	Nanomaterials	Green	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Fabrication and Surface Interactions of Super-Hydrophobic Silicon Carbide for Membrane Distillation		Scientific community		
AAU	2019	Nanomaterials	Green	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Surfactant-Assisted Fabrication of Alumina-Doped Amorphous Silica Nanofiltration Membranes with Enhanced Water Purification Performances		Scientific community		
AAU	2020	Nanomaterials	Green	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Desalination of Groundwater from a Well in Puglia Region (Italy) by Al2O3-Doped Silica and Polymeric Nanofiltration Membranes		Scientific community		
CNRS	Iug-05	Adsorption (Springer)	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Submission hold	Photoassisted regeneration of saturated activated carbons from a wastewater treatment plant: a case study (delayed submission, possible patenting)		Scientific community		
CNRS	Iug-05	Advanced materials for energy production,	Gold	Book chapter	Submitted	Synthetic strategies for the preparation of nanoporous carbons (submitted 2022)		Scientific community		
CNRS	Iug-05	Water Adsorption & Technology	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	In preparation	Competitive adsorption of water emerging pollutants on activated carbons: a case study (to be submitted end 2022)		Scientific community		
Technion	Aug-20	Nature Sustainability		Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Rethinking wastewater risks and monitoring in light of the COVID-19 pandemic	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41893-020-00605-	Scientific community	Policy makers	
Technion	Nov-21	Chemical Engineering Journal	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Towards on-demand photocatalysis: controlling the operation of a photocatalytic reactor based on real-time, automatic monitoring of toxicity towards the working	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1	Scientific community	Policy makers	
UPV	2021	Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering	gold	Peer-reviewed article	Accomplished	Humic like substances extracted from oil mill wastes in photo-Fenton processes: Characterization, performance and toxicity	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106862	Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Environmental science and Pollution Research	gold	Peer-reviewed article	Submitted	Effect of photo-Fenton process on inlet and outlet WWTP effluents and on CECs degradation from real WWTP waters.		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Nanomaterials	gold	Peer-reviewed article	Submitted	Regeneration of activated carbon filters by means of (photo)-Fenton process		Scientific community		
POLIMI	2020	Science of the Total Environment	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished			Scientific community		
POLIMI	2021	Water Resources Research	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished			Scientific community		
POLIMI	2022	Journal of Environmental Management	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	"Adoption of Water Reuse Technologies: An Assessment under Different Regulatory and Operational Alternatives", doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115389, Journal of Environmental Management, 317, 115389, 1-		Scientific community	Policy makers	Industry
POLIMI	2022	Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Integrating water reuse technologies in complex water systems planning and management: The case study of Apulia		Scientific community & Policy		Investors
POLIMI	2022	Environmental Modelling & Software	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	ICT-based decision-analytic platform (DAP) to support policy makers in selecting robust and efficient water planning portfolios, integrating traditional water management		Scientific community		
UARV	December, 2020	Journal of Cleaner Production	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Policy narratives of circular economy in the EU – Assessing the embeddedness of water and land in national action plans	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125685	Scientific community	policy makers	
UARV	March, 2021	Launch of a Special Issue on Water Journal (MDPI)	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Planning for water circular territories: drivers, barriers and best practices to foster transition	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/resources/special_iss	Scientific community	Policy makers	
UARV	May, 2022	Water Journal (Special Issue Water and Human Settlements of the Future on MDPI)	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Assessing the Inclusion of Water Circularity Principles in Environment-Related City Concepts Using a Bibliometric Analysis	https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/14/11/1703	Scientific community		
UARV	September, 2022	Water Journal (Special Issue Advance in Water Management and Water	Gold	Peer-reviewed Article	Accomplished	Governance Arrangements for Water Reuse: Assessing Emerging Trends for Inter-Municipal Cooperation through a Literature	https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/14/18/2789	Scientific community		
UARV	May, 2022	Water Management and Circular Economy (Elsevier Book, under revision)		Peer-reviewed Article	Submitted	Assessing policy and planning contexts for the transition to water circular economy: examples from southern Europe		Scientific community		
UARV	May, 2022	Water Management and Circular Economy (Elsevier Book, under revision)		Peer-reviewed Article	Submitted	Fostering the transition to water reuse: the role of institutional arrangements in the EU circular economy action plans		Scientific community		
UARV	May, 2022	Water Policy Journal (Under Revision)		Peer-reviewed Article	Submitted	Challenges for the transition to a water circular economy, assessing the influence of institutional arrangements		Scientific community		

b) Participation in Conferences and Workshops

Table 5.2 reports in details the participation in Conferences and Workshops. Project Ô was represented in 45 events, spread all over the Project duration with the exception of 2020, due to the sudden and unpredictable pandemic

emergency that suspended all in-person congress activities without yet having the time to reorganize them, when possible and deemed appropriate, remotely.

Table 5.2. List of participation to Congresses, Conferences and Workshops

Partner	Date	Place	Name of the event / journal	Type of material generated SELECT AN OPTION	Title of the material (if applies)	Link/Reference/Additional informations	Type of audience reached SELECT ONE OR MORE OPTIONS		
UNITO	2019	Portorose (Slovenia)	6th European Conference on Environmental Applications of Advanced Oxidation Processes (EAADP-6)	2 Posters	1) Development of a reactor for water purification based on a photocatalytic TiO2 coated solid support 2) PROJECT Ô: demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water. The key role of standardization	http://eaadp6.ki.si/	Scientific community		
UNITO	2021	online event	IWARR2021 - 4th International Water Association, Resource Recovery Conference	Presentation	How local, small loops of water management can allow a circular economy vision of the "resource" water.	https://www.iwar2021.org/	Scientific community	Industry	
UNITO	2022	Turin (Italy)	11th European Conference on Solar Chemistry and Photocatalysis: Environmental Applications (SPEA)	2 Oral Presentations	1) Employing Controlled Periodic Illumination to Evaluate the Photocatalytic Activity of a TiO2 Aqueous Slurry 2) Developing a TiO2 Supported Photocatalyst for Textile wastewater treatment	https://www.spea11.unito.it	Scientific community		
AAU	2018	Odense (Denmark)	Danish Chemical Society Annual Meeting 2018	Presentation			Scientific community		
AAU	2018	Side (Turkey)	1st Eurasian Environmental Chemistry Conference	Presentation					
AAU	2019	Turin	NIS colloquium - AQUAilty & Project Ô: AQUAilt	Presentation	Membrane materials for the abatement of micropollutants				
HSRW	2018	Malta	4th NUCLEUS Conference 2018	Poster			Scientific community	Policy makers	
HSRW	2018	Kleve (Germany)	Public Lecture Series: Future of water management: Hightech meets social innovation	Presentation			Civil society	Scientific community	
CNRS	2019	Toulouse (France)	Conference of the French Carbon Association	Presentation		https://sfec2019.sciencesconf.org/	Scientific community		
CNRS	2019	Lisbon (Portugal)	LIFE IMPETUS International Final Conference	Presentation	Coupling adsorption and photocatalysis for the removal and degradation of emerging pollutants	http://life-impetus.eu/2019/10/11/life-impetus	Scientific community		
CNRS	2022	Torino (Italy)	11th European Conference on Solar Chemistry and Photocatalysis: Environmental Applications (SPEA)	Presentation	Photoassisted Regeneration of Saturated Activated Carbons		Scientific community	Industry	
Technion	2018	Haifa (Israel)	IWA2018- International Conference on small water and wastewater systems	Presentation	An integrated photocatalytic-biological wastewater treatment approach utilizing an on-line control unit		Scientific community		
Technion	2018	Almaria (Spain)	The 10th European Meeting on Solar Chemistry and Photocatalysis: Environmental Applications	Presentation	An integrated photocatalytic-biological wastewater treatment approach utilizing an on-line control unit		Scientific community		
Technion	2018	Israel	The 15th Small Waste & Wastewater Systems	Presentation	An Integrated Photocatalytic-Biological Wastewater Treatment Approach Utilizing an On-line Control Unit		Scientific community	Industry	
Technion	2018	Tel-Aviv, Israel	Water Research in Israel: the next generation of research, management & industry	Presentation	An Integrated Photocatalytic-Biological Wastewater Treatment Approach Utilizing an On-line Control Unit		Scientific community	Industry	
Technion	2019	Israel	Meeting of the Israel Institute of Chemical Engineering.	Poster	Toxicity control utilizing reporting bacteria in integrated photocatalytic-bio wastewater system		Scientific community	Industry	
Technion	2022	Tel-Aviv (Israel)	Israel Chemical Society Annual Meeting	Poster	Developing and study of on-line biotoxicity sensing and control unit for wastewater treatment based on cell-viability monitoring assay		Scientific community		
UPV	2019	Portorose (Slovenia)	6th European Conference on Environmental Applications of Advanced Oxidation Processes	Presentation	Fluorescence spectroscopy as complementary tool for monitoring real wastewater treatment by advanced oxidation processes		Scientific community		
UPV	2019	Portorose (Slovenia)	6th European Conference on Environmental Applications of Advanced Oxidation Processes	Presentation	Fluorescence spectroscopy as a tool to control the integration of different wastewater reuses technologies in a circular economy model		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Sevilla (Spain)	XIV Congreso español de tratamiento de aguas (META)	Presentation	Estudio de la aplicación del proceso foto-Fenton en la degradación de contaminantes emergentes presentes en aguas de EDAR y en la eliminación de materia orgánica disuelta.		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Turin (Italy)	11 th European Photocatalysis: Conference on Environmental Solar Chemistry and Applications (SPEA)	Presentation	Photo-Fenton process effect on primary and secondary WWTP effluents and on Terbutylazine and Acetaminophen degradation.		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Turin (Italy)	11 th European Photocatalysis: Conference on Environmental Solar Chemistry and Applications (SPEA)	Presentation	Fluorescence spectroscopy as a tool to control the integration of different wastewater reuses technologies in a circular economy model		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Turin (Italy)	11 th European Photocatalysis: Conference on Environmental Solar Chemistry and Applications (SPEA)	Presentation	Bench scale prototype for the integration of active carbon and photo-Fenton process to remove pollutant in a circular economy model		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Cusco (Perú)	5 th Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (CIPOA).	Presentation	Effect of photo-Fenton process on inlet and outlet WWTP effluents and on CECs degradation from real WWTP waters.		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Cusco (Perú)	5 th Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (CIPOA).	Presentation	On the relevant role of iron complexation for the performance of photo-Fenton process at mild pH		Scientific community		
UPV	2022	Cusco (Perú)	5 th Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (CIPOA).	Presentation	Fenton-Like processes carried out by copper as a catalyst in high saline solutions		Scientific community		
POLIMI	2018	Palermo (Italy)	13th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES)	Presentation	"Analysing the Relationship between Wastewater Utility and Civil Society Stakeholders: First Evidence from Two Cases", SDEWES 2018, Palermo, Italy, September 30 - October 4, 2018.	Scientific community	Policy makers	Industry	
POLIMI	2019	Vienna (Austria)	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly	Presentation/Poster			Scientific community		
POLIMI	2019	Dubrovnik (Croatia)	14th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES)	Presentation/Poster			Scientific community		
POLIMI	2020	Dublin, Ireland	International Conference on Resource Sustainability (ICRS), Dublin, Ireland, June 30-July 2, 2020	Presentation/article	"Sewage sludge management options and civil society stakeholders' influence: first evidence from Italian cases",				
POLIMI	2021	Dublin (Ireland)	2021 International Conference on Resource Sustainability (ICRS 2021)	Presentation	Best Presentation Award "Sewage sludge management options and civil society stakeholders' influence: first evidence from Italian cases"	Scientific community	Policy makers	Industry	
POLIMI	2021	Dubrovnik (Croatia)	16th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES)	Presentation	"Water Reuse and Water Utilities: An Economic Framework"	Scientific community	Policy makers	Industry	
POLIMI	2021	Vienna (Austria)	European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly	Presentation/Poster		Scientific community			
POLIMI	2022	Milano (Italy)	2nd IFAC Workshop on Control Methods for Water Resource Systems Milano, 22-23 September 2022	Presentation	Surrogate modeling for water reuse planning in complex water systems. IFAC-PapersOnLine, 55(33), 111-116. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.11.018		Scientific community		
IRIS	2019	Venice (Italy)	IWARR	Presentation			Scientific community	Industry	Investors
IRIS	2019	Milan (Italy)	AQUARES workshop	Presentation			Scientific community	Civil Society, Policy makers	
UARV	2019	Aveiro	26th APDR Congress	Presentation	Water-wise planning for circular economy. The Guadiana river basin district case study.	http://www.apdr.pt/congresso/2019/	Scientific community	policy makers	civil society
UARV	2019	Aveiro	26th APDR Congress	Presentation	Water Framework Directive and the transition into a water circular economy – an analysis to explore such articulation	http://www.apdr.pt/congresso/2019/	Scientific community	policy makers	civil society
UAVER	2021	Aveiro	Research Seminars on SDG of the Centre of Governance, Competitiveness and Public Policies (GOVCOPP) on University of Aveiro	Presentation	Policy narratives of circular economy in the EU – Assessing the embeddedness of water and land in national action plans		Scientific community	civil society	
UAVER	2021	Aveiro	Research Seminars on SDG of the Centre of Environmental and Marine Sciences (CESAM) on University of Aveiro	Presentation	Policy narratives of circular economy in the EU – Assessing the embeddedness of water and land in national action plans		Scientific community	civil society	
UARV	2022	Aveiro	Research @DAO on University of Aveiro	Poster	Policy narratives of circular economy in the EU - Assessing the embeddedness of water and land in national action plans	https://www.eu-project-o.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Policy-narratives-of-circular-economy-in-the-EU-Assessing-the-embeddedness-of-water-and-land-in-national-action-plans.pdf	Scientific community	civil society	
UARV	2022	Aveiro	Research @DAO on University of Aveiro	Poster	Policy and planning settings for the transition to water circular economy - barriers and drivers in place	https://www.eu-project-o.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Policy-and-planning-settings-for-the-transition-to-water-circular-economy-barriers-and-drivers-in-place.pdf	Scientific community	civil society	
UARV	2022	Aveiro	Research @DAO on University of Aveiro	Poster	Institutional arrangements of water reuse: new challenges for the transition to a water circular economy	https://www.eu-project-o.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Institutional-arrangements-of-water-reuse-new-challenges-for-the-transition-to-a-water-circular-economy.pdf	Scientific community	civil society	
UNI	2019	Milan (Italy)	Webinar - MODULO 2. La normazione volontaria (UNIONCAMERE)	Other (webinar)			Industry	Scientific community	Standardization community
UNI	2021	Bologna (Italy)	R&I projects and standardization: the experience of Project Ô - participation to the	Other (speech)		https://www.pcc-club.com/download/Bonini/Poster.php?id=117	Industry	Scientific community	Standardization community
UNI	2019	Italy	BRIDGIT - Bridging the Gap between Research and Standardization	Presentation			Scientific community	Policy makers	
PARTICULA	2022	Zagreb (Croatia)	Textile-technology University	Presentation	Wastewater management in the textile industry - the example of the company Galeb d.d.		Scientific community		
Eilat City	2021	Eilat	IEEE lecture	Presentation	Eilat Smart City		Experts		
IOLR	2021	Online	Israel R&D Innovation cluster promoting mariculture and blue economy				Experts, investors, NGOs, government		

c) Workshop Organizations

In Table 5.3 the workshops organized by Consortium members are detailed. Compared to what reported in the DoA, there was a re-adjustment, in particular for activities scheduled in 2020 and 2021. In any case a higher number of events than the ones foreseen in DoA took place.

Table 5.3. List of workshops organized by Consortium members

Partner	Role	Date	Place	Name of the event / journal	Context	Type of material generated SELECT AN OPTION	Title of the material (if applies)	Link/Reference/Additional informations	Type of audience reached SELECT ONE OR MORE OPTIONS
SOCAMEX	Organiser and participant	2019	Almendralejo (Badajoz, Spain)	Project Ô presentation at workshop "Mejoras sostenibles en la gestión del agua y nuevas técnicas de tratamiento y reutilización del agua para una economía circular"	Consortium and public	Presentation	Demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated an symbiotic use of water.	No webpage available. News on the workshop in 4 local-regional newspapers	Scientific community Industry civil society
AAU	Organiser	2018	Aalborg (Denmark)	2nd AAU Seminar on Advanced Water Purification Technologies	Consortium and public	Presentation		Viewed also as a way to engage relevant local/regional stakeholders	Scientific community Industry Investors
HSRW	Organiser	2018	Argentina	Water Management and Circular Economy		Presentation			Scientific community Civil society Policy makers
HSRW	Organiser	2018	Costa Rica	Water Management and Circular Economy		Presentation			Scientific community Civil society Policy makers
HSRW	Organiser	2018	Mexico	Water Management and Circular Economy		Presentation			Scientific community Civil society Policy makers
CNRS	Organiser	2018	Gijón (Spain)	3 Iberoamerican Adsorption Symposium		Poster		https://41ia-ba3.com/	Scientific community Industry
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance:	Consortium and private	Other			Policy makers Industry civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance:	Consortium and private	Other			Policy makers Industry civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance:	Consortium and private	Other			Policy makers Industry civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance:	Consortium and private	Other			Policy makers Industry civil society
UNI	Organiser	2019	Milano	Standard, ricerca e innovazione: opportunità e sinergie - Milano, 22 ottobre 2019	Consortium and private	Other (webinar)		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=854&startart=ricerca-e-innovazione-opportunita-e-	Scientific community Industry Standardization community
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Costruire un futuro sostenibile con gli standard: modelli di consumo e gestione dell'acqua responsabili	Consortium and public	Other (webinar)		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=10037&model=di-di-consumo-e-gestione-dell-acqua-	Industry Scientific community Standardization community
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Economia circolare: sinergie tra settore pubblico e privato per progettualità innovative	Consortium and public	Other (webinar)		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=10063&secm	Industry Scientific community Standardization community
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Innovazione e standard per la sostenibilità ambientale: le opportunità del programma LIFE	Consortium and public	Other (webinar)		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=10158&image	Industry Scientific community Standardization community
POLIMI	Organiser	2022	Milano (Italy)	2nd IFAC Workshop on Control Methods for Water Resource Systems Milano, 22-23 September 2022	Consortium and public			https://cmwrs2022.dueb.polimi.it/	Scientific community

d) Industrial conferences.

Table 5.4 reports the participation and/or organization of events strongly oriented towards an industrial audience. As it can be seen the number of events and the number of Project partners involved is rather high, and also partner from academic sector are involved in some events.

This activity testifies to the liveliness of exchanges on issues related to the management of water resources, which involve multiple stakeholders.

Many of these events have benefited from the possibility of being carried out online and for this reason are distributed over time throughout the duration of the project and have suffered the impact of the pandemic emergency less heavily than other dissemination activities.

Events from e) to i) will be analysed together, while a paragraph will be devoted to give more insights about the International School on Water Reuse.

All these events are listed in Table 5.5. White papers are not present since partners considered that publishing open access was a better way to reach the scientific audience, while the other dissemination activities were more suitable to reach the other different target audience.

It can be observed that most of these activities were involving non-academic partners, thus allowing an overall wide participation to dissemination activities from all "sides" inside Project Ô Consortium.

This aspect is highly relevant when considering the relevance attributed to the disclosure of results in different environments, exploiting a wide portfolio of dissemination tools and addressing a plurality of stakeholders.

Table 5.4 List of “industrial” conferences and analogous events

Partner	Role	Date	Place	Name of the event / Journal	Type of material generated SELECT AN OPTION	Title of the material (if applies)	Link/Reference/Additional informations	Type of audience reached SELECT ONE OR MORE OPTIONS		
SOCAEMX	Participant	2018	Barcelona (Spain)	Smart City Expo World Congress	Presentation	Innovative solutions for urban and industrial activities involving water: a review of 4 European projects	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/the-event/past-editions-2018	Investors	Industry	Customers
SOCAEMX	Participant	2018	Madrid (Spain)	CONAMA 2018	Poster	Project O: cerrando el círculo	http://www.conama2018.org/web/es/conama-conecta.html	Scientific community	Industry	
SOCAEMX	Participant	2019	Venice (Italy)	IWARR 2019	Poster	"Tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water: the Project O"	http://www.iwar2019.org	Scientific community	Industry	
SOCAEMX	Participant	2019	Zaragoza (Spain)	EIP Water	Poster	Demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water.	https://www.eip-water.eu/eu-water-innovation-conference-2019-2	Industry	civil society	customers
SOCAEMX	Participant	2020	Online	EPIC Online Technology Meeting on Water Quality Monitoring	Presentation	Water Quality Monitoring: a view of a final user in the framework of water reuse	youtube.com/watch?v=16eBhwQ0B44	Industry	Scientific community	
HSRW	Participant	2021	Brussels (Belgium / online)	EASME Water Project Europe Event	Presentation	Inclusive Governance for a Water-Smart Society		Policy Makers	Industry	Scientific community
HSRW	Participant	2021	Denmark (online)	World Water Week	Presentation	More than just making waves: The deep waters of evidence-based science communication		Scientific community	Industry	Policy Makers
CNRS	Participant	2021	Orléans (France)	DREAM Stories: 10 years 100 projects. Workshop organized by pole DREAM of competitiveness	Presentation	Project O: Demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water		Scientific community	Industry	General Public
CNRS	Participant	2021	Webinar (international)	Event organized by the International Adsorption Society (webinar online)	Presentation	Adsorption from solution of emerging pollutants: from fundamentals for data interpretation to case studies		Scientific community	Industry	General Public
CNRS	Participant	2021	Muroi (France)	SFEC-2021 (Société francophone d'études du carbone)	Presentation	A photochemical approach for the regeneration of spent activated carbons		Scientific community	Industry	
CNRS	Participant	2021	Virtual	Carbon Chemistry and Materials CCM-21	Presentation	Photocatalyzed regeneration of activated carbons: a case study on a WWTP		Scientific community	Industry	
CNRS	Participant	2022	Orléans (France)	Journée Scientifique sur les micropolluants organisée par F. Guillou, INRAE, Univ. Tours CNRS – RTR MIDI	Presentation	Dégradation des perturbateurs endocriniens par procédés d'oxydation avancés: un exemple concret sur une station d'épuration d'eaux usées		Scientific community	Industry	
CNRS	Participant	2022	Orléans (France)	SFEC-2022 (Société francophone d'études du carbone)	Presentation	Modélisation de l'adsorption des polluants émergents sur charbon actif en systèmes mono et multicomposant		Scientific community	Industry	
CNRS	Participant	2022	Denver (USA)	Fundamentals of Adsorption Conference of the International Adsorption Society	Presentation	Competitive adsorption of emergent pollutants from solution on carbon-based adsorbents		Scientific community	Industry	
CNRS	Participant	2022	Orléans (France)	Scientific Workshop organised by Le Studium, Orléans, France	Presentation	Porous Carbons for Water Treatment: facing current pollution threats with advanced methods		Scientific community	Industry	
IRIS	Participant	2020	ONLINE	Economia circolare: sinergie tra settore pubblico e privato per progettualità innovative	Presentation			Scientific community	Industry	
IRIS + FPM	Participant	2020	ONLINE	FESTIVAL AVVIS. Costruire un futuro sostenibile con gli standard, modelli di consumo e	Presentation			Scientific community	Industry	
IRIS	Participant	2019	Rimini (Italy)	ECOMONDO	Presentation			Scientific community	Industry	
IRIS	Participant	2019	Milan (Italy)	Standard, ricerca, innovazione: una partnership vincente	Presentation and panel session				Industry	
IRIS	Participant	2018	Yokohama (Japan)	WCEF world circular economy forum	Pitch presentation				Industry	Scientific community
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance: fostering the transition water reuse (Almendralejo)	Other			Policy makers	Industry	civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance: fostering the transition water reuse (Lecce)	Other			Policy makers	Industry	civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance: fostering the transition water reuse (Omis)	Other			Policy makers	Industry	civil society
UARV	Organiser	2022	Online	Co-creation for innovative planning and governance: fostering the transition water reuse (Eilat)	Other			Policy makers	Industry	civil society
UNI	organiser	2019	Milano	Internal meeting with stakeholder	Other			Policy Makers	Industry	
UNI	Participant	2019	Milano	Webinar - MODULO 2. La normalioe volontaria	Presentation			Industry		
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Costruire un futuro sostenibile con gli standard: modelli di consumo e gestione dell'acqua responsabili	Presentation		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=full&id=9837-modelli-di-consumo-e-gestione-dell-acqua-responsabili-un-webinar-2-7-ottobre&catid=171&Itemid=2612			
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Economia circolare: sinergie tra settore pubblico e privato per progettualità innovative	Presentation		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=full&id=9838-economia-circolare-sinergie-tra-settore			
UNI	Organiser	2020	online	Innovazione e standard per la sostenibilità ambientale: le opportunità del programma LIFE	Presentation - Standard		https://www.uni.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=full&id=9838-innovazione-e-standard-per-la-sostenibilita			
PARTICULA	organiser	2020	Rovinj (Croatia)	project O presentation on Ruđer Bošković Institute	presentation			Scientific community		
PARTICULA	organiser	2021	Zagreb (Croatia)	project O presentation on Ruđer Bošković Institute Zagreb	presentation			Scientific community		
PARTICULA	organiser	2021	Zagreb (Croatia)	project O presentation on Agricultural University of Zagreb	presentation			Experts		
PARTICULA	organiser	2021	Zagreb (Croatia)	project O presentation on Croatian Chamber of Commerce	presentation			Industry		
PARTICULA	organiser	2022	Zagreb (Croatia)	Zagreb- Faculty of technical engineering and technology	Presentation	Textile industry wastewater- characterization and treatment options		Scientific community		
Kalundborg	Organiser	2021	National, DK	Presentation of Project O for my ERFA gruppe	Presentation	Project O	SWANA ERFA group member	Water experts	Industry	
Kalundborg	Organiser	2021	Kalundborg (Denmark)	Bestyrelsesmøde i Kalundborg Symbiose	Presentation	Project O	local members of Kalundborg Symbiosis	Board members	Industry	Water Utility
Kalundborg	Organiser	2021	Kalundborg (Denmark)	Advisory Board meeting, Kalundborg Symbiose	One-pager	Water reuse and technology challenges	Advisory board of Kalundborg Symbiosis	Board members	Industry	Water Utility
Kalundborg	Organiser	2021	Kalundborg (Denmark)	Strategi-workshop, KS-Advisory Board	Strategic paper	Strategi in KS - water perspectives	Advisory board of Kalundborg Symbiosis	Board members	Industry	Water Utility
Eilat City	Lecturer	2019	Israel/Beer Sheva	lecture for municipal environmental experts	Presentation			Experts		
Eilat City	Lecturer	2019	Eilat	Lecture for students from WPI/Boston	Presentation			Engineering dep.		
Eilat City	Lecturer	2021	Eilat	IEEE lecture	Presentation	Eilat Smart City		Experts		
Eilat City	Lecturer	2021	Online	XII SMART CITY FORUM - Poland	Presentation	Eilat Smart City		Experts		
Eilat City	Lecturer	2021	Online	C-Talk Takaw	Presentation	Eilat Smart City		Experts		
IOLR	Lecturer	2019	Reichman University (IDC)	International Course Sustainability Entrepreneurship	Presentation	Filling gaps to meet future aquaculture challenges		Students		
IOLR	Lecturer	2021	Online	Israeli R&D innovation cluster promoting mariculture and blue economy and Rural Development of Israel	Presentation	Sustainable Mariculture	visit project O demosite	Experts, investors	NGO's	government
IOLR	Organiser	2022	IOLR-NCM, Eilat (Israel)	Meeting with Zalul Environment Association				Experts, investors		

6. Long lasting dissemination activities.

Project Ô encompassed with a pluridisciplinary approach the key aspects of polluted water treatment and reuse, in the context of the Circular Economy perspective and promoting the “fit for purpose” approach in order to tailoring the quality of the reclaimed water in the function of the needs for its reuse.

A huge effort has been done under the technological point of view in order to have in place in the 4 demosites the suites of technologies as industrial prototypes to be tested. On the other side decisional platforms have been developed to assist water planners and to pave the way to a proper market for the water reuse.

Inside the Dissemination action it was agreed among partners the relevance of evidencing the cultural legacy of the Project and the choice fell on the foundation of an **International School on Water Reuse** featuring the unique aspect, among other schools dealing with waters, of facing the water reuse under a systemic and multidisciplinary perspective.

The School has therefore a **multidisciplinary character** and approaches the Water reuse under different perspectives, spanning from water treatment technologies to social expectation and acceptance, from integrated decisional platforms for policy makers to industrial symbiosis and business models within water and related benefits.

All these sectors involve a variety of disciplines and actors, each one with their own language. To tackle in a wide and complex dimension the water reuse requires an extensive interaction between these disciplines and actors, in a context of reciprocal confidence and respect. Moreover, a progressive **learning of the key issues of the different languages** belonging to each discipline is needed in order to achieve a **mutual comprehension**, yielding **efficient communication** and **synergies**.

This **multidisciplinary interaction** constitutes an enormous asset for the School, towards the participants (teacher and students), at the present time as well as in a long lasting perspective.

Under this perspective, the School aims to promote the progressive structuring and enrichment of a multidisciplinary communication, that must be nourished and evolve, in order to be vital and productive.

The School as an “agora”, a meeting and multi-directional exchange place for reinforcing the multidisciplinary communication where every participant can give his/her own contribution and enrich him/herself with others’ contribution.

One of the challenges of the School lies therefore in being able to bring together the complexity of the individual disciplines and issues necessary to understand and communicate the water reuse as a whole, despite not possessing all the specific skills in depth.

At the same time, **the School must provide specific insights on the various topics** that contribute to define the water reuse theme. The **other challenge**, therefore, **will be the ability to equip the School with a suitable structure to fulfill both the need to improve specialist knowledge and the intent to promote a multidisciplinary debate**.

To this end, specialist lessons could be held on the various disciplinary aspects, alternating with multidisciplinary round tables. A final workshop involving teachers and students (for groups) working on real cases of water reuse could represent a suitable tool to integrate specialist and multidisciplinary aspects.

The School will **run annually** and will be aimed at PhD students, young researchers, young professionals interested in deepening knowledge and skills in the management of water resources as well as at policy makers, NGOs, investors, companies, representants from sectors where water can be reused (first of all from agriculture).

The school has the **ambitious goal** of becoming well-known and internationally recognized as a reference point for the topic of Water reuse.

The first edition has been released in September 2022 at the Chemistry Department of the university of Torino (Italy) and the Figure 2 summarizes the School's scopes and perspectives

Figure 2. Schematic Summary of the International School on Water Reuse

The following five main thematic pillars have been identified:

1) *Policies, plans and regulations for water reuse*

- Water reuse in the context of circular economy: concepts, policies and plans in the EU context
- Drivers and barriers of water reuse: regulations and guidelines
- Costs and benefits of water reuse – financial and nonfinancial
- Challenges for integrated, equitable and plural water governance
- Integrated platform for decision making

2) *Technologies: state of the art and challenges*

- Assessment of appropriated treatment technologies for different kind of polluted waters to guarantee a safe reuse
- Strategies for water characterization (toxicity, biodegradability, adapted analytical tools...)
- Preliminary, primary, secondary and tertiary treatments: potential for energy and material recovery (nutrients, sludges after anaerobic digestion...)
- Water disinfection: innovation and challenges
- Advanced engineered treatments; design and operational aspects

3) *Indicators and monitoring schemes and tools*

- Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing
- KPIs to ensure the quality in water reuse
- The role of standardization
- Risk assessment: hazard identification, exposure assessment, dose-response assessment

4) Social awareness and acceptance

- Public involvement to raise spread awareness
- Social-Life Cycle assessment
- Social acceptance and water education

5) Case studies, water reuse and symbiotic experiences

- **Speed up water reuse at European level**
- Water reuse from sludge treatments for fertigation and vertical farming
- Water reuse and nutrients recovery from mariculture

To the first edition of the School participated as Lecturers 14 people belonging to Project Ô's partners, as evidenced in yellow in the School program reported in Figure 3.

UNIVERSITÀ DI TORINO Butterfly Area chimica project Ô

INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL ON WATER REUSE
19-21 SEPTEMBER 2021
TORINO – CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT

Scientific Program
19th September 2022

9:00-9:30 Institutional greetings
9:30-10:00 Climate change and water scarcity; from present to future troubles (M.Lasagna, University of Torino, Italy)
10:00-11:00 Wastewater reuse in Europe. New EU regulation and challenges for stakeholders (L.Rizzo, University of Salerno, Italy and P.Simon, Water treatment plant Murcia, Spain)
11:00-11:20 COFFEE BREAK
11:20-11:50 Water reuse from sludge treatments for fertigation (L.Celi, University of Torino)
11:50-12:20 VALUE CE-IN – “VALorisation of treated wastewater and slUdge in view of Circular Economy and Industrial symbiosis” (L.Petta, ENEA, Italy)
12:20-12:40 Water reuse: drivers and barriers at policy, planning and governance levels (T. Fidelis, University of Aveiro, Portugal)
12:40-13:00 Business models for small and local loops of water reuse (M.Lai, IRIS, Italy)
13:00-14:00 LUNCH BREAK
14:00-16:00 ROUND TABLE: Drivers and barriers to speed up water reuse in Europe.
Speakers: P.Simon (Murcia, Spain), D.Mainero (ACEA Pinerolese, Italy), L.Petta (ENEA, Italy), V.Maunno (University of Torino, Italy), A. Battilani (Irrigants d'Europe), R. Maffettone (EC, JRC, Ispra, Italy), I.Macsinga (University of Timisoara, Romania), M.Lai (IRIS srl, Italy)
Chairs: A.Bianco Prevot (University of Torino, Italy), L.Rizzo (University of Salerno, Italy)
16:00-16:20 COFFEE BREAK
16:20-18:30 Reuse adoption: Framework and tools (P. Garrone, A. Nen, M.Micotti, Politecnico di Milano, Italy and E.Weber, Fondazione Politecnico di Milano, Italy)

20th September 2022

9:00-12:00 Visit to a local water utility (ACEA Pinerolese S.P.A., Pinerolo)
13:00-14:00 LUNCH BREAK
14:00-18:30 Technologies for water treatment and reuse: state of the art and challenges.
Chairs: A.Arques (Polytechnic University of Valencia, Spain), M.Minella (University of Torino, Italy)
14:00-14:30 Introduction to AOPs, Basic concepts on Reactive Species (M. Minella, University of Torino, Italy)
14:30-15:30 State of the art and challenges for the scale-up of AOPs up to the industrial level: Fenton processes and heterogeneous photocatalysis (A. Arques, Polytechnic University of Valencia, Spain; V. Maurino, University of Torino, Italy)
15:30-16:00 Solar-based advanced oxidation processes: the long experience at the PSA (S. Malato, Plataforma Solar de Almeria, Spain)
16:00-16:20 COFFEE BREAK
16:20-17:00 Membrane and reactive membranes: introduction and engineering aspects (V. Boffa, University of Aalborg, DK; A. Tiraferri, Polytechnic of Torino, Italy)

21st September 2022

9:00-10:15 Application of narrative methodologies for awareness raising and education on water reuse issues (B.Bruschi and M.Repetto, University of Torino)
10:15-11:30 Public involvement to raise spread awareness and Social acceptance of innovative solutions. (A.Petcu, University of Timisoara, Romania)
11:30-11:45 COFFEE BREAK
11:45-13:00 Conceptualize a social acceptance challenge and see how it could be assessed empirically. The Project O experience (E.Jensen and L. Sayles, Institute for Methods Innovation, Ireland)
13:00-14:00 LUNCH BREAK
14:00-15:30 Team working on a specific case study: Almeria and Murcia (Spain): two areas one next to the other: water reuse or not reuse? This is the question (I. Oller, Plataforma Solar de Almeria and P.Simon, Water treatment plant, Murcia, Spain)
15:30-16:00 Update on water reuse guidelines at european level (R.Maffettone, EC, JRC, Ispra, Italy)
16:00-16:20 COFFEE BREAK
16:20-16:55 The role of Water Footprint Metrics in water use management (A.Manzardo, UNI, Italy)
16:55-17:15 The role of standardization in the water reuse; a brand new toolkit (C.Di Maria, UNI, Italy)
17:15-17:45 Open challenges and future perspectives
17:45-18:00 Closing remarks

Figure 3. Program of the 1st edition of the International School on Water Reuse

Other 18 people, scientists from academic and non-academic research institutions, members of EU Institutions, from water utilities and from Agriculture association, were involved as Lecturers as well. The School was attended by 25 applicants coming from different European countries. Seminar, round tables and workshops were adopted to present the School topics, in order to stimulate the active participation and maximize the interaction among all participants (lecturers and “students”).

The first edition of the School was therefore a great opportunity to strengthen existing collaborations and establishing new ones, reinforcing the network of the participants.

The first follow up was the establishment, at the University of Torino, of a multidisciplinary Working Table on water reuse, aiming at becoming an interlocutor recognized by the regional institutions for the implementation of the EU regulation on the reuse of urban wastewater in agriculture, which will come into force in June 2023.

7. Conclusion.

From the analysis of the Dissemination action in its various components (goals, strategy, and activities) emerges the image of a multidirectional action, homogeneously distributed over time and among the partners of the Consortium, differentiated in the activities according to the characteristics of the partners and the roles performed in the project.

The Dissemination action reflects the articulated nature of the Project, the positive aspect of which is certainly the possibility of working in synergy by bringing together the various skills. A possible risk could have been that of a dispersive and ineffective action, with duplication of interventions and areas left uncovered.

This did not happen thanks to a detailed planning work of the Dissemination already within the Project and to a constant monitoring of its implementation.